

CDIO and Biomimicry: a case of study of analysis of the enhanced structural masonry interlock with the nacre interlacing solution

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Abstract

This article seeks to discuss possible contributions of addressing the environmental issue as an optional standard for the Conceive, Design, Implement and Operate - CDIO methodology. In turn, the environmental approach was based on Biomimetics in which models of nature serve as inspiration for the design of products and processes to solve human problems. In this article, the development of a students' project of the civil engineering course carried out in an optional course at PUC-SP with the union of the methodologies of CDIO and Biomimicry will be detailed. The general objective of the optional course was to create a Biomimetic engineering solution: students should choose a problem to be worked on and, from that, they should seek inspiration in nature through analysis of morphological, physiological, anatomical characteristics of living beings or even in phenomena nature to develop the conception of your project. The project described here adopted as an object of study the improvement of the interlocking of structural masonry with the use inspired by Nacre: from the analysis of Nacre's morphology, the students sought to reproduce the interlocking characteristics of this material that would influence its resistance. Through the union of CDIO and Biomimetic methodologies, students had the possibility to develop research and prototyping skills, competences, hypothesis testing and product validation. It was possible to understand in practice how the concepts of physics, mechanics of solids and strength of materials are applied to the prototype. More than the inclusion of the issue of sustainability in engineering education and in the 12 CDIO standards, inspiration in nature can assist in the development of research and innovations for engineering products, processes and systems.

Key words: CDIO Standards, Biomimicry, Masonry interlock improvement, Sustainability.

1 Introduction

This article seeks to discuss possible contributions of addressing the environmental issue as an optional standard for the Conceive, Design, Implement and Operate - CDIO methodology. In turn, the environmental approach was based on Biomimetics in which models of nature serve as inspiration for the design of products and processes to solve human problems.

The context of this proposal is connected to the evolution of the 12 CDIO Standards: originated in the 1990s in the Aeronautics and Astronautics program at Massachusetts Institute of Technology - MIT, the CDIO methodology emerged to meet demands for a teaching-learning method that engineering students should be able to work on theoretical knowledge and, simultaneously, they could develop a set of soft skills. In 2001, version 1.0 of the CDIO Syllabus was developed and, later, in 2004, the international CDIO initiative was created with the participation of 10 schools. In 2005/2007, 12 standards were proposed for the implementation of the methodology. These standards have undergone a reformulation in 2014 giving rise to Syllabus 2.0 followed by additions in 2016, generating the version of Syllabus 2.1. According to MALMQVIST et al, "*The standards define the distinguishing features of a CDIO program, serves the guidelines for educational reform, enable benchmarking with other CDIO programs and provide a tool for self-evaluation-based continuous improvement*". (MALMQVIST et al, 2020, p.48)

In 2017, discussions for Syllabus 3.0 have emerged: for Malmqvist et al. (2017, p. 21) once external context of engineering education has evolved, the CDIO approach must be evolved as well. In this version of Syllabus comes the proposal to create "optional CDIO standards", which would be added to the original twelve standards, now called "core CDIO standards". (apud MALMQVIST et al, 2020, p. 48). Both optional and core

CDIO standards have come to address the environmental issue in a perspective of enabling future engineers to work with sustainable lifecycles for products, processes and systems.

Since 2016, the CDIO methodology has been applied in conjunction with Biomimetics in an optional undergraduate engineering course at the Pontifical Catholic University of São Paulo - PUC-SP. Previous results have shown to be very promising in instigating the creation of innovative and sustainable engineering solutions. (RAGGI, MUNHOZ, & NORIEGA, 2018) According to Janine Benyus "*Biomimicry is a new science that studies nature's models and then imitates or takes inspiration from these designs and processes to solve human problems*". (BENYUS, 1997, p. 6) In this article, the development of a project for students of the civil engineering course carried out in this optional course with the union of the methodologies of CDIO and Biomimicry will be detailed.

2 Scope

The general objective of the optional course was to create a Biomimetic engineering solution: students should choose a problem to be worked on and, from that, they should seek inspiration in nature through analysis of morphological, physiological, anatomical characteristics of living beings or even in phenomena nature to develop the conception of your project.

In the last semester of 2020, the course was offered to a class of 16 civil engineering students. They were divided into 4 groups and each chose a working problem. In a period of approximately 4 months, students should conceive, design, implement and operate a prototype, seeking in nature the inspiration to solve the problem. This article describes the study developed by one of these groups.

The project described here adopted as an object of study the improvement of the interlocking of structural masonry with the use inspired by Nacre: from the analysis of Nacre's morphology, the students sought to reproduce the interlocking characteristics of this material that would influence its resistance.

3 Teaching-Learning Methodology

The teaching-learning methodology was structured through the project lifecycle proposed by CDIO, passing through the stages of Conceive, Design, Implement and Operate.

During the 2nd semester of 2020, the students conceived the project by researching the characteristics of constructive pathologies and possible solutions to be adopted inspired by beings and phenomena of nature through Biomimetics.

After developing the scope of the proposal, activities were oriented towards the realization of the prototype project. Given that the entire prototyping stage would be carried out in the midst of the COVID-19 pandemic, and that access to materials and laboratories at the university were greatly compromised, students were instructed to carry out simplifications in the project in order to make their construction and testing viable. In that instance they use accessible and available resources in their own homes.

Once the design and planning of the testing stage was established, the development of a prototype for concept testing was stipulated. In this intermediate prototype, the students were able to verify the viability of their ideas and possible implementation problems.

After correcting the problems found, the students were instructed to develop the final prototype in order to carry out the implementation and operation analyzes. In view of the results obtained, students should check the potential and limitations of the prototype. The objectives of the study developed by the students as well as the motivation of this study are described below.

4 Study Objective and Motivation

According to (SAMPAIO, 2010), of the varied pathological manifestations that can appear in the structural masonry, the fissures and cracks stand out. The appearance of these pathologies can occur when fragile raw

materials of ceramic, concrete and mortar blocks are subjected to tensile, bending, shearing, mortar retraction efforts, among others. The area most affected by such damage is the interlocks, which corresponds to the region with the least resistance in the set, as shown in figure 1.

Figure 1. Fissure in the interlocking of Structural Masonry retrieved from (Oliveira, 2016, p. 7)

This study aims to seek solutions to reduce the occurrence of cracking and cracking pathologies, ensuring improvements in the interlocking of structural masonry. It starts from the concept of Biomimetics, which according to BENYUS (1997) consists of science that studies the solutions of nature in order to imitate them or be inspired to solve human problems.

After researching different solutions from nature, it was found that the morphology of the mollusk shells allowed the optimization of their resistance. The main characteristic observed was the existence of interlaced plates called nacre in the shells, as shown in figure 2. According to MATTER (2005), nacre has an interlacing that allows it to increase its resistance. It is an iridescent material composed of aragonite, with fixation carried out by organic layers on its surface consisting of protein, guaranteeing the flexibility of the material and the union of the interlacing. In tests, it was found that such a set guarantees a resistance to nacre 3000 times greater than that obtained in aragonite alone.

Figure 2. Nacre example retrieved from (EWA et al., 2019) and Figure 3. Morphology of Nacre retrieved from (IDRIS; FRANCOIS, 2016, p.390)

In percentages of constitution, Nacre has 5% of its weight composed of organic material of proteins and polysaccharides; the remaining 95% consist of hexagonal-shaped aragonite, stacked in a staggered arrangement, similar to the structural masonry block wall, as shown in figure 3, with the plates twisted in relation to each other by 5%, with sinking overlapping the neighbor by 20%" (MATTER, 2005).

MATTER (2005) complements that the composition and constitution of the nacre guarantees resistance both to the efforts of traction and compression, as well as resists catastrophic failures that in other structures result in the propagation of cracks. Its composition has greater tenacity, that is, it needs more energy to generate fractures or plate breakage. And even if for some reason it starts a crack, the hexagonal shape of its parts will make transmission difficult.

Based on this principle, the improvement of structural masonry was sought through the reproduction of these morphological characteristics. We sought to apply such properties to prototypes, the description of which was elaborated below.

5 Work Plan

5.1 Materials and Methods

In order to carry out tests on a model inspired by nacre, some prototypes were proposed for experimentation, using materials of easy access and handling listed below on table 1:

Table 1. List of using materials

List of using materials	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plaster; • Gray adhesive cementitious mortar; • Adhesive AC III White mortar; • Water; • Wooden base; • Sledge hammer; • Books, and weights to serve as cargo; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scale to measure loads; • Hexagonal Ice Forms (1.25 x 1.25 x 2 cm); • Rectangular Ice Shapes (1.5 x 1 x 1 cm); • Strings; • Spatulas and sandpaper for blocks and arrangements; • Ruler for measuring columns.

Once the research was carried out in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, due to the limitations of access to laboratories and materials, the choice of accessible raw materials was chosen amid a lack of resources. In this context, plaster was used to shape the blocks as a representative of the bricks used in Structural Masonry. Plaster was chosen because it is a water-repellent material, easy to access and handle, in addition to quick drying.

The volumetric trace used was 1: 7 of water and plaster, with the aid of ice molds in hexagonal and rectangular shapes. Blocks of an equivalent area of 1.5 cm² were built. With the dry blocks, hand-held fittings were made in the hexagonal blocks: hen subjected to compression, the blocks are "tied" providing greater resistance to the structure in the same way as the entanglement observed in the nacre, as shown in figures 4, 5 e 6.

Figure 4. (left) Molding of rectangular blocks and Figure 5. (center) Molding of hexagonal blocks Figure 6. (right) Hexagonal block

Two systems for comparison were set up, both measuring 10 x 10 x 8 cm under the same wooden base: (I) rectangular blocks, imitating the shape of common bricks, and (II) hexagonal blocks inspired by nacre Morphology. Both systems were grouted with 1: 2 mix mortar with water and cement, as can be seen in figure 7.

Figure 7. Systems assembled with hexagonal and rectangular blocks.

Resistance tests were started on both systems for comparative analysis.

5.2 De Description of Experiment

5.2.1 Phase 1 of the Experiment - Concept Test Prototype

The prototypes of rectangular and hexagonal blocks were assembled using the gray adhesive mortar. From this, two types of tests were performed: one with static load under the system, and the other with dynamic load through free fall, as shown in figures 8, 9 and 10:

Figure 8. Assembled Prototypes (left) Figure 9. (center) Static Load Test and Figure 10. (Right) Mobile Load Test

For the test of resistance to static efforts, school materials (books and notebooks) were used as a load, juxtaposed on the molded system, totaling a weight force of 200N. As a result, it was noticed a crushing in the mortar of the system composed of rectangular blocks, however, both systems resisted well, without showing signs of rupture.

In turn, dynamic load tests were carried out with the aid of a 1.2Kg sledgehammer (approximately 12N). The sledgehammer initially at rest was tied to a string and aligned vertically with the molded systems. In sequence, it was repeatedly launched in free fall with varying height, obtaining the following results shown in table 2:

Table 2. Results obtained in the first experiment with dynamic load

Distance (cm)	Rectangular Blocks System	Hexagonal Blocks System
25	No visible effect	No visible effect
30	No visible effect	Beginning of cracking in the mortar, with the blocks still interlocked
35	Crushing and deformation of the system	Break of the system, but without breaking the blocks
40	Break of the system with breaking the blocks	-

Phase 2 of the Experiment - Final Prototype

After the dynamic load tests of the first phase of the experiment, possible flaws in the molded system were analyzed and proposals were made that could improve the performance for the next phase.

In the assembly of the new prototypes, the improvement occurred through the interlocking, which was rethought from the arrangement of the blocks in the mortar. Also, it was used the AC III White Flexible Adhesive mortar, with a higher degree of elasticity than that previously used in phase 1, with a function similar to the protein structure existing between the nacre plates, as shown at figures 11 and 12.

Figure 11. New hexagonal prototype and Figure 12. New rectangular prototype

Following the same test method with dynamic load, the following results were shown in table 3:

Table 3. Results obtained in the second experiment with dynamic load

Distance (cm)	Rectangular Blocks System	Hexagonal Blocks System
20	No visible effect	No visible effect
25	No visible effect	No visible effect
30	No visible effect	No visible effect
35	The first cracks appear	Flattening at its bottom base
40	It remained stable	It remained stable
45	It remained stable	It remained stable
50	Appearance of more significant cracks	It remained stable
55	It remained stable	It remained stable
60	It remained stable	Small cracks only at the ends
65	Larger size cracks	It remained stable
70	Partial system disruption occurs	It remained stable
75	A complete disruption of the system occurs	It remained stable only with partial rupture on the sides

Figure 13. Dynamic Load Tests / Result System with hexagonal blocks and System with rectangular blocks

The tests continued until the mallet was launched at a height of 100 cm, but the system inspired by nacre morphology, with the hexagonal blocks, remained stable and did not break completely. In sequence, analyzes were made on the results obtained.

5.3 Result Analysis

In the first phase of testing, the system composed of rectangular blocks proved to be more effective than the hexagonal ones. It is believed that this fact occurred due to the lack of horizontal interlocking in the system inspired by nacre, where the arrangements of its blocks were just stacked on top of each other. In addition, the inserts made in the hexagonal shaped blocks were made by hand due to lack of resources, which made them irregular and not uniform.

Figure 14. Assembly of phase 1 prototypes

In this way, the means of assembly and molding used were studied, so that new tests could be carried out, as well as the implementation of improvements. In addition to the use of AC III mortar with a high degree of elasticity, in the interlocking of the hexagonal blocks the fittings were not molded, thus directing a greater focus to the arrangement of the interlocked blocks.

Figure 15. Application of improvement in phase 2

In the results of the second phase, it was possible to notice that the system inspired by nacre's morphology showed an improvement in its performance, becoming more resistant compared to the rectangular block system.

Despite this, it is important to consider the scarcity of resources for research and the lack of reliability in the results, considering that both systems were molded by hand, together with the load tests that were not carried out on suitable equipment, due to the lack of access to laboratories.

6 Analysis of Potentiality and Limitations

The main limitations of the study are found in the manual execution of the block samples, lack of access to materials managed to reproduce the elasticity generated by the protein layer of connection between nacre and the impossibility of using laboratories to create a controlled and reliable environment for the performance comparisons.

However, despite these limitations, it was possible to see a significant increase in the resistance of the hexagonal blocks in the second test phase (the beginning of the break occurred with strikes 15 cm higher than in the case of the rectangular blocks). The solution presented a satisfactory result, demonstrating that there is potential for improvement in the model through greater technological control in the prototyping and testing phases.

7 Continuity Plan

Through the union of CDIO and Biomimetic methodologies, students had the possibility to develop research and prototyping skills, competences, hypothesis testing and product validation. More than that, it was possible to understand in practice how the concepts of physics, mechanics of solids and strength of materials are applied to the prototype.

If further studies show an increase in the resistance of a set of hexagonal blocks connected by flexible structures, the application of these blocks in civil construction could optimize the use of construction materials, implying a reduction in costs and in the environmental impacts of civil construction. Research may be proposed as a result of this initial study, with the use of construction materials creating hexagonal blocks used with mortars with high elasticity.

8 Conclusion

Due to processes of natural selection and evolution, morphological, physiological and anatomical characteristics of living beings or even the very balance of biotic and abiotic systems can become a repository of knowledge. More than the inclusion of the issue of sustainability in engineering education and in the 12 CDIO standards, inspiration in nature can assist in the development of research and innovations for engineering products, processes and systems.

From the teaching point of view, it is believed that the union of CDIO and Biomimetics methodologies can contribute to the generation of meaningful learning and environmental awareness. The creation of a product based on a specific problem, and which is solved through Biomimetics allows the valorization of the environment not only as a source of natural resources, but also as a repository of knowledge. At the same time, through the construction of the prototype, students transform abstract knowledge related to the exact sciences into tools for the stages of design, implementation and operation.

In turn, from the point of view of learning, it is believed that two points deserve to be highlighted: (I) the limitations imposed by the Covid-19 pandemic and (II) the CDIO learning methodology. In relation to the limitations imposed by the pandemic, the change from the face-to-face classes to remote activities demanded greater focus and dedication on the part of the students. Despite this, the use of digital platforms has made it possible to shorten distances between students and teacher, enabling more agile and frequent communication. Teachers have become more accessible through digital platforms. A challenge found in this scenario was consequently the lack of access to materials and laboratories. Despite the limitations, the creativity to establish a comparative method allowed students to work with adverse conditions. In contrast, the CDIO learning methodology showed students a better way to execute and understand the results and stages of a work, in a way that is consistent with the reality of an engineering project life cycle and also giving the possibility to acquire a greater assertiveness in the results.

With these observations it can be concluded that the scenario in which the group encountered difficulties, but in return demanded from the students more dedication, patience, focus, group work, and especially more creativity. The experience acquired by the group as a team engaged students in the learning process.

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